

Simulation of micro crack formation in a magnesia spinel refractory during the production process

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Abstract

Frequently refractory brittleness is reduced by introduction of micro cracks during the production process. With finite element methods the crack initiation and formation in a magnesia-spinel refractory during the cooling stage of the firing process is simulated in a two dimensional representative volume element. The microstructure is described by a random spatial distribution of spinel and magnesia grains surrounded by a magnesia matrix. The grain size distribution was chosen according to the Dinger Funk equation. Crack formation due to a thermal misfit between magnesia and spinel is described by the concrete damaged plasticity material model provided by the commercial software ABAQUS. After cooling the model shows a reduced brittleness and a crack pattern typically for this kind of material. The obtained mechanical properties of an afterwards simulated tensile test are compared with literature values. The simulation provides reasonable values and is capable to reproduce micro cracking in the presented refractory.

Keywords: refractory, micro-cracking, simulation, periodic boundary conditions, tensile failure

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1. Introduction

1.1 Influence of micro cracks on refractory properties

Refractory materials are applied in industrial high temperature processes. In case of a thermal shock the materials have to sustain mechanical loads due to a constrained thermal expansion. Different thermal shock parameters were developed to characterise and compare refractories. For example the thermal shock resistance parameters R proposed by Kingery [1] which describes a critical temperature difference for crack initiation is defined by:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_t}{E \cdot \alpha} \cdot (1 - \nu) \quad (1)$$

This parameter depends on the material's tensile strength σ_t , Young's Modulus E , thermal expansion coefficient α and the Poisson's number of lateral contraction ν . Another important parameter regarding the resistance against further crack propagation after crack initiation, is the thermal shock damage resistance parameter R'''' according to Hasselman [2]. It can be used to compare the degree of damage of various materials. Recently the characteristic length l_{ch} , firstly introduced by Hillerborg [3] and closely related to R'''' , gains importance to describe the brittleness of materials:

$$l_{ch} = \frac{G_f \cdot E}{\sigma_t^2} = 2 \cdot R'''' \quad (2)$$

Here G_f is the specific fracture energy for forming two fracture surfaces. With increasing characteristic length, an unstable crack propagation and brittle failure is less likely. The value of l_{ch} is dominated by the materials strength, as can be seen from equation (2). By reducing σ_t and thus increasing E/σ_t^2 while maintaining G_f , the resistance against further crack propagation can be increased significantly [4]. As can be seen from equation (1) and (2), R and R'''' do not depend on the strength σ_t in the same way. A rising strength causes a high crack initiation resistance but also causes a more brittle behaviour. Examples of experimental results of different refractories are given in Table 1. Here σ_{NT} is the nominal notched tensile strength determined by a wedge splitting test according to Tschegg [4].

Table 1: Some experimental results of different refractories [5]

Material	σ_{NT} [MPa]	E [GPa]	G_f [Nm ⁻¹]	l_{ch} [mm]
burnt magnesia 97 wt%	9.97	110	168	186
burnt magnesia 6 wt% Fe ₂ O ₃	11.8	105	189	143
magnesia spinel 10 wt% Al ₂ O ₃	3.91	33.8	147	325
magnesia spinel 3.4 wt% Al ₂ O ₃	3.41	33.7	187	544

The addition of spinel (MgAl₂O₄) to a pure magnesia (MgO) refractory reduces the strength and increases the thermal shock resistance [5]. This has also been observed in the work of Aksel et al. by investigations of the influence of different content of fine spinel and MgO grains < 0.01 mm [6] [7] [8] [9]. Fractographic investigations of various refractories with additives showed a micro crack network after the production process that is responsible for the reduced brittleness [6] [10]. In a similar work Grasset-Bourdel et al. investigated the influence of the spinel content with a grain size between 1 mm and 3 mm. Two different testing methods have been applied to evaluate the material properties, the wedge splitting test [4] [11] and a tensile test, respectively. The addition of 5 wt% spinel to pure magnesia nearly doubled the characteristic length and the fracture energy. At the same time the strength and the Young's Modulus are reduced significantly. The investigation of a spinel content up to 25 wt% provided similar results for the characteristic length whilst the strength is further reduced. Despite different absolute values between the testing procedures, the trend is the same for both methods [12]. In another fractographic approach to characterize the brittleness reducing micro cracks, Harmuth et al. linked the decrease of brittleness not only to the strength reduction due to micro cracks, but also to the interfacial crack path amount [5] [13] [14]. Magnesia products show high transgranular (intragranular) crack propagation. However in spinel refractories the micro cracks are mainly located between grains along the grain/ matrix boundary where the bonding strength is supposed to be lower than the strength of magnesia matrix [5] [6], and in the matrix itself.

Micro cracks are believed to form during the cooling stage of the production process by a thermal misfit between magnesia and spinel. At the firing temperature the microstructure is believed to be mainly stress free due to relaxation because of creep. Then during cooling the larger thermal expansion coefficient of magnesia α_m leads to compressive stress in the grains and tensile hoop stresses in the matrix during

cooling as schematically shown in Figure 1. When these stresses near the grain interface exceed the materials strength, a micro crack is initiated.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of micro-cracking during cooling with a thermal expansion misfit, $\alpha_g < \alpha_m$, showing radial compressive and tensile hoop stresses

1.2 Scope of the presented work

Among a few others [15] [16] this work intends to place the first steps towards the simulation of microstructural evolution for magnesia-spinel bricks during the cooling stage of the firing process. This also should reveal whether all processes associated and partly quoted above have been understood sufficiently. Extensive simplifications will be necessary, and it is therefore not the goal to accurately simulate actual material properties. Whether the presented approach is a meaningful step or not should be assessed in the following manner: On the one hand results of the most essential mechanical properties should at least be similar to those observed in experiments (Table 1). On the other hand, also the crack path propagation should show similarities with fractographic results [5] [13] [14]. Moreover a goal of this research is to identify further necessary efforts to improve this kind of micromechanical simulation. This includes on the one hand details about parameter settings, on the other hand also a discussion of the fundamental simulation principle used.

2. Modelling a magnesia spinel structure

In order to simulate the micro cracking observed in a magnesia spinel refractory, its structure has to be represented with the most important heterogeneity, the spinel. Due to the complexity of the material several simplifications became necessary.

2.1. Grain distribution

The whole material is graded according to Dinger-Funk [17] where spinel grains between 1 mm and 5 mm are randomly embedded in the matrix. In the first approach the matrix consists of MgO modelled as a homogeneous material. Later, in an extended model variable portions of magnesia grains > 1 mm are explicitly considered additionally to the spinel grains. Then the matrix material contains all grains smaller than 1 mm. The percentage smaller than a given grain size d_i is calculated according to [17]:

$$P(d) = \frac{d_i^n - d_{\min}^n}{d_{\max}^n - d_{\min}^n} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

Here n is the distribution modulus, d_{\min} is the minimum and d_{\max} is the maximum grain size. The optimum value for a densest packing of spherical grains is expected for n equal to 0.37 [17], which was chosen

here. The theoretical grain size distribution of the model is divided into five grain fractions as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Grain size distribution according to the Dinger-Funk equation (3) with $n = 0.37$, $d_{min} = 0$ mm and $d_{max} = 5$ mm divided in 5 fractions. Bars indicate the percentage of each fraction.

The percentage for each grain fraction GF_i in Figure 2 is calculated from:

$$GF_i = \frac{d_{i+1}^n - d_i^n}{d_{max}^n - d_{min}^n} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

Here d_{i+1} and d_i are the upper and lower diameter of the grain fraction GF_i . For the distribution shown in Figure 2, the maximum grain size is 5 mm and the distribution modulus n is equal to 0.37. The percentage for each fraction is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Grain size fraction according equation (3), $n = 0.37$, $d_{min} = 0$ mm and $d_{max} = 5$ mm, spinel = vol%

Sample	grain size [mm]	fraction		total [%]
		spinel [%]	magnesia [%]	
GF ₄	4 - 5	1.76	6.16	7.92
GF ₃	3 - 4	2.07	7.23	17.22
GF ₂	2 - 3	2.57	8.96	28.75
GF ₁	1 - 2	3.59	12.53	44.87
Matrix	< 1		55.13	100
Σ		10	90	100

According to the used grading more than 55 % of the material is smaller than 1 mm and the remaining 45 % are allocated among the grain fractions $GF_1 - GF_4$.

In order to represent the spinel content in the magnesia matrix the coarsest grain fraction must be described by at least one grain. The corresponding smallest possible edge length of the model can then be determined by the area of the smallest grain of the coarsest grain fraction in the following manner:

$$(a_{\min})^2 \cdot \frac{vol_{grains}}{100} \cdot \frac{GF_{\max}}{100} \geq \frac{(d_{\min,GF_{\max}})^2 \cdot \pi}{4} \quad (5)$$

Here a_{\min} is the minimal edge length of the 2D model and vol_{grains} is the volume percentage of the spinel grains in the model, GF_{\max} is the volume percentage of the coarsest grain fraction and $d_{\min,GF_{\max}}$ is the smallest grain diameter of the coarsest grain fraction. The domain size of the model is small compared to a whole brick hence a representative volume element (RVE) with special boundaries is used for an infinite continuation. The here used term RVE refers to a model of the material that is used to determine the corresponding effective properties, e. g. stress and strain. As illustrated in Figure 3, the domain size a of the RVE is small compared to a sample l_M , but still sufficiently large to correctly represent all essential information about the microstructure e. g. the grain size d .

Figure 3: Definition of a 2D RVE for a statistically homogeneous material

The use of a RVE has the advantage to save computational costs by reducing the number of elements. More details and a recent review about RVEs can be found elsewhere [18] [19].

2.2. Periodic boundary conditions

An important issue of RVEs are the boundaries of the model. It is reasonable that a macroscopic sample is composed of adjacent RVEs so that opposite sides show the same deformation and stress states. The consequence for a 2D model, as can be seen in Figure 4, is that the distance l for any pair of points that exactly lie on opposite edges is the same. This special behaviour of the boundaries of the RVE is achieved by an application of so called periodic boundary conditions (PBC) [20]. The function and implementation of PBC is briefly explained here.

Figure 4: Periodic boundary conditions with edges Γ_{ij} , points $x_{i, \Gamma_{ij}}$ and corners C_i

The displacement of points $u(x_{i, \Gamma})$ on edges Γ consists of the macroscopic displacement due to a macroscopic strain, $\bar{\varepsilon} \cdot x_{i, \Gamma}$, and the periodical displacement, $u^*(x_{i, \Gamma})$, caused by material heterogeneities. The latter describes the periodic deformation of the edge.

$$u(x_{i, \Gamma}) = \bar{\varepsilon} \cdot x_{i, \Gamma} + u^*(x_{i, \Gamma}) \quad (6)$$

Here $x_{i, \Gamma}$ is the i -th point on an edge and the periodical displacement of this point is $u^*(x_{i, \Gamma})$. Because the periodic part of the equation is equal for opposite sides, e. g. $u^*(x_{i, \Gamma_{23}}) = u^*(x_{i, \Gamma_{14}})$, the macroscopic displacement between opposite points is:

$$u(x_{i, \Gamma_{23}}) - u(x_{i, \Gamma_{14}}) = \bar{\varepsilon} \cdot (x_{i, \Gamma_{23}} - x_{i, \Gamma_{14}}) \quad (7)$$

This is valid for x - and y -direction according to the coordinate system in Figure 4. In the used software ABAQUS periodic boundary conditions are implemented by using constraint equations and reference points, RP^{ij} , to link opposite sides:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_x(x_{i, \Gamma_{14}}) - u_x(x_{i, \Gamma_{23}}) - u_x(RP^{11}) &= 0 \\ u_y(x_{i, \Gamma_{14}}) - u_y(x_{i, \Gamma_{23}}) - u_y(RP^{12}) &= 0 \\ u_x(x_{i, \Gamma_{12}}) - u_x(x_{i, \Gamma_{43}}) - u_x(RP^{21}) &= 0 \\ u_y(x_{i, \Gamma_{12}}) - u_y(x_{i, \Gamma_{43}}) - u_y(RP^{22}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{for } 0 \leq i \leq m \quad (8)$$

Here $u_x(RP^{11})$ and $u_y(RP^{22})$ indicate the displacement perpendicular between two opposite sides; $-u_x(RP^{11})$ equals the right side of equ. (7). Further m is the number of nodes on one edge. More information about the validity and the implementation of PBC is given elsewhere [21] [22] [23].

2.3. Definition of material behaviour

The applied Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model of ABAQUS provides the capability of modelling the inelastic behaviour during the cooling of the refractory [24]. In the presented simulations only the tensile failure is permitted and is represented by a plasticity model based on the work of Lubliner [25] and modified by Fenves [26]. A possible stress-strain response of the material under uniaxial tension is shown in Figure 5. Until the tensile strength $\sigma_{t,y}$ is reached the material behaves linear elastically.

Figure 5: Stress-strain behaviour of the concrete damaged plasticity model under tensile loading

With ongoing displacement, strain softening behaviour according to Hillerborg's fictitious crack model [3] represents the material response. The total strain is the sum of the elastic and the plastic strain $\epsilon_{t,tot} = \epsilon_{t,el} + \epsilon_{t,pl}$. When the stress at the crack tip reaches the tensile strength a crack is initiated and the post-failure behaviour is then specified by the fracture energy.

The stress does not drop to zero immediately after the crack tip, but will decrease by consuming energy according to:

$$G_f = \int_0^{x_{t,ult}} \sigma(x) dx_t \quad (9)$$

With further increase of the crack opening width x_t more fracture energy is consumed. For a crack opening equal or larger than $x_{t,ult}$, the stress in an element is reduced to zero.

2.4. The finite element model

The chosen edge length of the quadratic RVE for the simulation is sufficient to have at least one grain of the coarsest fraction GF_4 at any given spinel content. In this simulation 10 vol% spinel is considered. The minimal model size according to equation (5) is $a_{min} = 26.7$ mm while the chosen model edge length is $a = 35$ mm. A random spatial distribution of grains is achieved via an in-house developed python script during the pre-processing step of the simulation. Starting with the coarsest size fraction, grains are generated and placed within the RVE as long as there is enough space for at least one grain of the smallest size of the current fraction. If the percentage of the actual grain fraction is depleted the next smaller fraction is used for the generation of grains. This procedure lasts until there is no more area for a further grain of the finest fraction. The grains are placed anywhere within the model boundaries without overlapping each other. If a grain intersects one or even two boundaries, the part of the grain that is outside will be completed on the opposite edge(s). The model is meshed automatically by ABAQUS using the advanced front algorithm and quad-dominated linear generalized plain strain coupled thermal-displacement elements (CPEG4T) [24]. Figure 6 shows a model with 10 vol% grains created in the pre-processing step, the edge length is $a = 35$ mm.

Figure 6: RVE with 10 vol% spinel and 90 vol% matrix, $a = 35$ mm

3. Simulation of the cooling stage and the tensile test

For all simulations the commercial finite element (FE) software ABAQUS is used. The interface zone between grains and matrix is described by cohesive surfaces and behaves similar to the matrix. This allows a contact opening and interfacial crack propagation along grain boundaries. In this first simulation approach only tensile cracking in the matrix is permitted, transgranular cracking is not considered. It is not necessary to consider the creep influence at the typical firing temperature of about 1600 – 1700 °C [7] [8], because the material relaxes to a nearly stress free state [27]. The calculation then starts at 1200 °C assuming a stress free initial state. A low cooling rate (0.02 K/s) and the small size of the RVE justify the assumption of a homogeneous temperature in the model at any time. The material properties of Table 3 are used and considered as independent of temperature.

Table 3: Material properties used for the simulations [16] [28] [29]

Material	E [GPa]	$\sigma_{t,v}$ [MPa]	α [10^{-6} K^{-1}]	G_f [Nm^{-1}]
Matrix	110	7	13.6	100
MA-spinel	210	-	7.5	-
MgO	300	-	13.6	-

After the cooling stage and the formation of the micro crack network, a displacement controlled tensile test is simulated to obtain the resulting mechanical properties of the material.

The simulation result in Figure 7 shows the maximum in-plane principal stresses after cooling a model with 10 vol% (8.3 wt%) spinel from 1200 °C to 1190 °C only. All grains are under compression, the hoop stresses in the surrounding matrix have not yet reached the tensile strength $\sigma_{t,v}$. At this early stage of the cooling simulation there are still unstressed areas especially in regions without grains in the nearby.

Figure 7: Stress distribution (Pa) of a model with 10 vol% MA spinel after cooling from 1200 °C to 1190 °C

First micro cracks are formed after a temperature difference of about $\Delta T = -11$ °C. The final micro crack network at end temperature is represented by plastic strains in Figure 8. High values of plastic strains can be found around and between grains. Again there are also areas in regions apart from grains still showing no plastic deformations.

Figure 8: Resulting plastic strain pattern of a model with 10 vol% MA spinel after cooling from 1200 °C to 25 °C

A typical crack pattern that arises during the evaluation of the mechanical properties by a tensile test can be seen in Figure 9. The picture shows the result of an applied horizontal displacement of a vertical edge of the model. At the shown state the model is considered as fully divided into two pieces by a macro crack. Involved elements near grains reach the maximum stress in the circumferential direction before the stress at the interface becomes critical in the radial direction. Due to this a bond opening between grains and matrix cannot be observed.

Figure 9: Plastic strain pattern after tensile test in x-direction showing a localized crack on the left side

The localized macro crack in Figure 9 near the left edge propagates about 60 % in the matrix and 40 % along the interface between grains and matrix.

Ten simulations with the same properties as defined above and different arrangement of the grains were carried out to obtain the mean properties of a material containing 10 vol% spinel grains. The average stress-strain curve and the standard deviations illustrated in Figure 10 are showing good agreement, especially for the ascending part of the curve.

Figure 10: Averaged stress-strain response of ten simulation results with standard deviation.

All models show a reduced strength and a strongly lowered Young's Modulus compared to the initial material. There is also an important increase of the fracture energy. The mean result of the macroscopic tensile strength is $\sigma_t = 5.2$ MPa, the Young's Modulus is $E = 35$ GPa calculated from the slope in the origin, and the fracture energy is $G_f = 187$ Nm⁻¹. This is larger than values measured by Grasset-Bourdel et al [12] for a magnesia spinel and a grain size between 1 mm and 3 mm. The deviation between the FEM model and the measured value may arise due to strong contact properties. This is further considered in the following paragraph.

3.1. Influence of interface strength and the contact fracture energy

In order to become aware of the influence of interfacial contact characteristics, simulations applying one and the same model with a variation of the contact properties were performed. The stress-strain

responses of four different interfacial contact strengths $\sigma_{t,c}$, 7 MPa, 3 MPa, 1 MPa and 0 MPa, respectively, with a contact fracture energy $G_{fc} = 100 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ can be seen in Figure 11. The results of different contact fracture energies with fixed contact strength of $\sigma_{t,c} = 7 \text{ MPa}$ is shown in Figure 12. A separation of grains from the matrix can be observed when the contact strength is lower than the matrix strength, $\sigma_{t,c} < \sigma_{t,v}$, and partly with decreased G_{fc} . In the case of a very weak contact, $\sigma_{t,c} = 1 \text{ MPa}$, this separation takes place in an early stage of the cooling. One should bear in mind that normally during the cooling the matrix transfers a compressive stress to the grains and the separation is due to stress gradients caused by the heterogeneous material structure.

Figure 11: Influence of interfacial contact strength on the tensile strength of a 10 vol% spinel material with $G_{fc} = 100 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$.

The results of the variation of contact properties are summarized in Table 4. With the exception of the characteristic length all investigated properties are reduced with decreasing contact strength or contact fracture energy.

Figure 12: Influence of interfacial contact fracture energy on the tensile strength of a 10 vol% spinel material with $\sigma_{t,c} = 7 \text{ MPa}$.

Table 4: Influence of different contact characteristics on mechanical properties

Contact strength	Contact fracture energy	σ_t	E	G_f	l_{ch}
$\sigma_{t,c}$	G_{fc}				

[MPa]	[Nm ⁻¹]	[MPa]	[GPa]	[Nm ⁻¹]	[mm]
7	100	5.4	38.9	157	213
3	100	4.0	32.9	109	224
1	100	2.7	27.1	104	392
0 ^a	100	2.5	25.3	63	260
7	50	5.3	38.3	151	208
7	10	3.9	35.5	81	187
7 ^a	0	2.5	25.3	63	260

^a actually there is no bond between grains and matrix

It is interesting that there is no notable difference when G_{fc} is reduced from 100 Nm⁻¹ to 50 Nm⁻¹. Two simulations marked with a super script *a* show actually no bond between grains and matrix. Both models therefore show identical results.

3.2. Influence of interfacial crack paths

After showing the importance of the contact properties, the model is extended by MgO grains as a third discretized material to increase the heterogeneity of the model. This leads to an even more realistic structure. Due to the same assumed thermal expansion coefficient of the newly introduced MgO grains and the magnesia matrix, the occurring thermal stresses are only caused by the spinel grains. However by considering the interfacial zone of the third material, the influence of the contact properties on the stresses and further on the material characteristic increases with higher MgO content. The crack path of the macro crack is then not only depending on the spinel but also on the MgO contacts. Weak contacts are much more likely to promote propagation of the crack along the interfaces. For the following simulations the specific fracture energy of $G_f = 196 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ is chosen for the matrix according to experimental results [12]. The contact properties are set to be lower than the properties of the matrix, $\sigma_{t,c} = 6 \text{ MPa}$ and $G_{fc} = 10 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$, respectively.

A resulting crack path and the observed separation due to brittle contacts in a model with 30 vol% MgO and 10 vol% spinel is shown in Figure 13 (a). The distribution of both, MgO and spinel and the crack path, marked by a two-colour line, is shown in Figure 13 (b). The line in Figure 13 (b) distinguishes between the propagation of the crack in the interfacial zone and in the matrix. This corresponds to a fractographic procedure reported in [5].

Figure 13: Material with 10 vol% spinel and 30 vol% MgO grains after a tensile test showing the evaluation of crack path regions. In figure (a) the crack is depicted as a plastic strain with green and red elements. Open contacts are white and the spinel grains are pink. In figure (b) the spinel is green and the MgO is red. The crack propagation along a grain is marked by a red line. The crack path in the matrix is marked with a black line.

An analysis of the crack path propagation in four models with different magnesia grain content and the obtained mechanical properties are summarized in Table 5. The increase of the percentage of grains and the weak contact definitions lead to lower strength and Young's Moduli.

Table 5: Influence of 10 vol% MA grains with additional MgO content on crack path, $\sigma_{t,c} = 6$ MPa, $G_{fc} = 10$ Nm⁻¹

Grain content: 10 vol% MA	σ_t	E	G_f	l_{ch}	Crack along the interface	Macro crack length / model length
[vol% MgO]	[MPa]	[GPa]	[Nm ⁻¹]	[mm]	[%]	[%]
+ 0	4.7	35	196	310	49	127
+ 10	3.8	37	160	410	52	130
+ 20	3.7	34	138	343	58	132
+ 30	3.4	29	124	311	69	129

Table 6: Correlation matrix of the results from Table 5

	Aggregate content (MgO)	σ_t	E	G_f	l_{ch}	Crack along the interface	Macro crack length / model length
Aggregate content (MgO)	1						
σ_t	-0.92	1					
E	-0.80	0.52	1				
G_f	-0.98	0.97	0.66	1			
l_{ch}	-0.18	-0.22	0.69	-0.01	1		
Crack along the interface	0.96	-0.82	-0.92	-0.89	-0.37	1	

Macro crack length / model length	0.50	-0.66	0.07	-0.65	0.45	0.25	1
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From Table 6 the correlation of the percentage of MgO grains with the quantity of the interface crack propagation can be clearly seen. The grain MgO content which raises the interfacial crack path length influences all values except the ratio macro crack length to model length. The properties σ_t , E and G_f are also influenced by the amount of interface introduced by the higher grain content. In these simulations the contacts behave in a totally brittle manner and lead to this questionable correlation which is not supported by experience. Therefore another series of simulations with less brittle contacts has been performed. The contact properties are set to be $\sigma_{t,c} = 6$ MPa and $G_{fc} = 137$ Nm⁻¹, respectively.

Table 7: Influence of 10 vol% MA grains with additional MgO content on crack path, $\sigma_{t,c} = 6$ MPa, $G_{fc} = 137$ Nm⁻¹

Grain content: 10 vol% MA	σ_t	E	G_f	l_{ch}	Crack along the interface	Macro crack length / model length
[vol% MgO]	[MPa]	[GPa]	[Nm ⁻¹]	[mm]	[%]	[%]
+ 0	6	34.6	317	303	45	118
+ 5	5.9	36.6	293	311	42	114
+ 10	5.9	37.4	348	371	42	114
+ 15	5.9	37.6	332	358	56	116
+ 20	5.9	37.2	358	382	55	123
+ 25	5.8	37.9	303	341	54	119
+ 30	5.8	38.0	312	352	59	130

The results from this simulations in Table 7 show that the strength as well as the Young's Moduli do not change with increasing MgO content as strong as in the previously simulations. This behaviour can be explained by the fact that the very brittle contacts ($G_{fc} = 10$ Nm⁻¹) have consumed nearly all their fracture energy during the cooling stage, while in contrast the contacts in this simulations with $G_{fc} = 137$ Nm⁻¹ have still some fracture energy left. Consequently the material with higher G_{fc} shows overall more resistance against fracture during the tensile test. This can also be concluded by comparing the resulting fracture energies in Table 5 and Table 7.

Table 8 shows the correlation matrix calculated from the results of Tab. 7.

Table 8: Correlation matrix of the results from Table 7

	Aggregate content (MgO)	σ_t	E	G_f	l_{ch}	Crack along the interface	Macro crack length / model length
Aggregate content (MgO)	1						
σ_t	-0.83	1					
E	0.83	-0.86	1				
G_f	0.05	0.35	0.11	1			
l_{ch}	0.58	-0.29	0.69	0.79	1		
Crack along the interface	0.84	-0.53	0.58	0.14	0.48	1	
Macro crack length / model length	0.74	-0.44	0.31	0.00	0.24	0.76	1

While Tab. 8 shows apparently a clear correlation between the MgO content and the strength, the Young's Modulus and the crack amount in the interface, at least for the strength and the Young's

modulus this will probably not be observable in experiments as the dependency might be lower than the scatter associated with brick manufacture. But, contrary to Tab. 6, the negative correlation of Young's modulus with the amount of grains has changed to a positive one. This can be explained by the higher Young's Modulus of the MgO grains and the more intact contacts between matrix and MgO grains. Also the resulting specific fracture energy becomes independent from the MgO content. There are less already opened interfaces in the structure and the additional contacts provide further consumable energy during the tensile test.

4. Conclusion and further proceedings

The presented FE simulation model is able to produce a typical micro crack network that arises during the cooling stage of a freshly produced magnesia spinel refractory material. It is necessary to define contact properties and considering an interface between grains and matrix to obtain mechanical properties close to experimental values and a realistic stress-strain response. It has been shown that the material characteristic is clearly affected by the chosen contact properties (strength and/or fracture energy). This has been further proved by considering additional contacts introduced by a varying MgO grain content. A following investigation of the resulting macro crack paths show that the amount of interfacial crack path propagation is also influenced by the contact properties. Brittle contacts lead to a longer macro crack path and to higher macro crack propagation in interfacial zones. The comparison of simulation results with very brittle and less brittle contact definitions show that it is a very important but also crucial task to choose appropriate values for the contact properties to address the materials behaviour.

With the presented model a first approach towards simulating the micro crack formation in a magnesia refractory during the first cooling process is achieved. The simulation results show that it is important to consider the interfaces to obtain results comparable with experimental ones. However, the presented model is limited by a lower grain size for spinel and MgO grains considered in the model. This limitation can be reduced by refining the mesh size, but with the disadvantage of increased computational costs and numerical instabilities. In general the discrete element method may have advantages to overcome the mentioned problems. A further possible improvement is the extended discrete element method XDEM. It offers a possibility for taking into account thermodynamics and a coupling to CFD and FEM.

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References

- [1] W. D. Kingery, "Factors affecting thermal stress resistance of ceramic materials," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 3-15, 1955.
- [2] D. Hasselman, "Unified theory of thermal shock fracture initiation and crack propagation in brittle ceramics," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 52, no. 11, pp. 600-604, 1969.
- [3] A. Hillerborg, M. Modéer and P.-E. Petersson, "Analysis of crack formation and crack growth in concrete by means of fracture mechanics and finite elements," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 773-781, 1976.
- [4] E. Tschegg, „Equipment and appropriate specimen shapes for tests to measure fracture values“. Austria Patent 390328, 31 1 1986.
- [5] H. Harmuth and R. Bradt, "Investigation of refractory brittleness by fracture mechanical and fractographic methods," *Keramische Zeitschrift*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 264-269, 2010.
- [6] C. Aksel and P. D. Warren, "Thermal shock parameters [R, R'" and R''"] of magnesia spinel composites," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 301-308, 2003.
- [7] C. Aksel, B. Rand, F. L. Riley and P. D. Warren, "Thermal shock behaviour of magnesia spinel composites," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 2839-2845, 2004.
- [8] C. Aksel, B. Rand, F. L. Riley and P. D. Warren, "Mechanical properties of magnesia-spinel composites," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 745-754, 2002.
- [9] C. Aksel, P. D. Warren and F. L. Riley, "Magnesia-spinel microcomposites," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. 3119-3128, 2004.
- [10] H. Harmuth and E. K. Tschegg, "A fracture mechanics approach for the development of refractory materials with reduced brittleness," *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, vol. 20, no. 11, pp. 1585-1603, 1997.
- [11] E. Tschegg, "New equipments for fracture tests on concrete," *Materialprüfung*, vol. 33, pp. 338-342, 1991.
- [12] R. Grasset-Bourdel, A. Alzina, M. Huger, T. Chotard, R. Emler, D. Gruber and H. Harmuth, "Tensile behaviour of magnesia-spinel refractories: Comparison of tensile and wedge splitting tests," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 913-923, 2013.
- [13] H. Harmuth, "Characterisation of the Fracture Path in Flexible Refractories," *Advances in Science and Technology, Trans Tech Publications*, vol. 70, pp. 30-36, 2010.
- [14] H. Harmuth, "Flexibility of refractories - fracture mechanical and microscopic Investigations," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference Refractories, Furnaces and Thermal Insulations*, 2010.
- [15] R. Grasset-Bourdel, A. Alzina, M. Huger, D. Gruber, H. Harmuth and T. Chotard, "Influence of thermal damage occurrence at microstructural scale on the thermomechanical behaviour of

magnesia–spinel refractories," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 989-999, 2012.

- [16] R. Grasset-Bourdel, "Structure/property relations of magnesia-spinel refractories: experimental determination and simulation," 2011.
- [17] D. R. Dinger and J. E. Funk, "Particle-Packing Phenomena and Their Application in Materials Processing," *MRS Bulletin*, vol. 22, pp. 19-23, 12 1997.
- [18] R. Hill, "Elastic properties of reinforced solids: Some theoretical principles," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 357-372, 1963.
- [19] I. Gitman, H. Askes and L. Sluys, "Representative volume: Existence and size determination," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 74, no. 16, pp. 2518-2534, 2007.
- [20] J. Michel, H. Moulinec and P. Suquet, "Effective properties of composite materials with periodic microstructure: a computational approach," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 172, pp. 109-143, 1999.
- [21] R. Smit, W. Brekelmans and H. Meijer, "Prediction of the mechanical behavior of nonlinear heterogeneous systems by multi-level finite element modeling," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 155, pp. 181-192, 1998.
- [22] O. van der Sluis, P. Schreurs and H. Meijer, "Homogenisation of structured elastoviscoplastic solids at finite strains," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 499-522, 2001.
- [23] V. P. Nguyen, M. Stroeve and L. J. Sluys, "Multiscale continuous and discontinuous modeling of heterogeneous materials: A review on recent developments," *Journal of Multiscale Modelling*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 229-270, 2011.
- [24] "Abaqus/CAE User's Manual v6.12".
- [25] J. Lubliner, J. Oliver, S. Oller and E. Onate, "A plastic-damage model for concrete," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 299-326, 1989.
- [26] J. Lee and G. Fenves, "Plastic-Damage Model for Cyclic Loading of Concrete Structures," *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, vol. 124, no. 8, pp. 892-900, 1998.
- [27] S. Jin, H. Harmuth and D. Gruber, "Compressive creep testing of refractories at elevated loads - Device, material law and evaluation techniques," *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, vol. 34, no. 15, pp. 4037-4042, 2014.
- [28] J. F. Shackelford and W. Alexander, *CRC materials science and engineering handbook*, 2010.
- [29] S. Burnett and U. K. A. E. Authority, *Properties of Refractory Materials*, Atomic Energy Research Establishment, 1969.

